

Digital Twins as Asset Management Support for Urban Drainage Systems: a modelling framework for fast assessment of Nature-based Solutions' conditions

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ABSTRACT

Urban Drainage Systems (UDSs) are increasingly challenged by ageing infrastructure, rapid urbanization, and the impacts of climate change. Nature-Based Solutions (NBSs), such as green roofs and swales, can enhance UDS performance and resilience, yet traditional Asset Management (AM) approaches primarily focus on grey infrastructure. To ensure optimal functionality, both grey and blue-green components must be systematically monitored and maintained. This study presents a Digital Twin (DT)-based framework for the rapid assessment of NBS conditions through continuous model updating. The proposed method employs a Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) controller to dynamically adjust simulation model parameters (e.g., surface roughness, hydraulic conductivity) based on real-time sensor observations. Parameter changes are interpreted as indicators of NBS condition, serving as early warnings for maintenance or intervention. The methodology will be tested on a section of the Belgrade UDS, focusing on a hypothetical green roof scenario. Water level data collected from the nearby sewer network will be assimilated into the model to update NBS parameters. The results aim to demonstrate the potential of DTs as effective asset management tools for monitoring and maintaining hybrid urban drainage systems.

1. Introduction

Increasing challenges, such as ageing infrastructure, climate change, and rapid urbanization are placing additional pressure on Urban Drainage Systems (UDS), often leading to reduced performance. Numerous studies have demonstrated the potential of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) to enhance UDS's performance and increase their resilience (Deletic et al. 2020). However, traditional Asset Management (AM) practices for UDS primarily focus on grey infrastructure (Cherqui et al. 2024) while NBS often remains overlooked. To maintain and improve overall system functionality of UDS, both grey and blue-green infrastructure must be included in inspection and maintenance strategies.

Application of digital technologies, such as Digital Twins (DTs), can significantly enhance AM of UDS. DTs represent virtual replicas of real systems that combine sensor data with simulation models, enabling real-time monitoring, condition assessment, and resource and contingency planning (Bartos and Kerkez, 2021; Kim et al., 2025). As NBS have become essential in modern stormwater management, their integration into DTs is essential for strengthening urban resilience to climate and infrastructure stresses. This research presents a method for the fast assessment of NBS conditions through continuous update of simulation model parameters based on sensor data.

2. Methodology

This study proposes a model-updating algorithm for rapid NBS condition assessment. Here, condition refers to the physical and functional state of key NBS components, such as clogging level or hydraulic capacity, which directly affect system performance.

The method evaluates the condition indirectly through performance monitoring and simulation model parameters updating accordingly. Key model parameters, including surface roughness and hydraulic conductivity, are linked to physical degradation processes. For instance, reduced conductivity detected through model updating can indicate clogging.

The simulation model is continuously updated (i.e. recalibrated) to reflect real NBS system performance. Updating is conducted using a Proportional–Integral–Derivative (PID) controller, which adjusts parameters according to sensor observations within the UDS (see Figure 1). Persistent parameter changes are treated as warning signals of NBS deterioration and the need for maintenance.

Fig. 1. A model-updating algorithm for fast NBS condition assessment

3. Case Study: New Belgrade Urban Drainage System

Fig. 2. a) case study, b) anticipated results

The application of the proposed methodology is illustrated for a section of the Belgrade UDS, which covers a highly urbanized area (see Figure 2a). Within the study, a hypothetical test scenario examines a large green roof system through the proposed model parameters update procedure (Figure 1). Water level data is collected from the nearby sewer network and used to update NBS model parameters, providing insights into the current condition of the green roof. Utilizing the PID controller during the simulation enables fast model parameter update (Figure 2b).

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